

Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain

D8.1 Market Analysis and Uptake Strategy

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ACRONYMS LIST

iFMS	Intelligent Fish Management System
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
WHO	World Health Organization
UN	United Nations
EFCA	European Fisheries Control Agency
EU	European Union
PESTLE	Political Economic Social Technologic Legal Environmental Factors
SWOT	Strengths Weaknesses Opportunities Threats
UML	Unified Modelling Language

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The TraceMyFish Consortium aims at commercially exploiting the output of the project, the intelligent Fish Management System (iFMS), so to enhance the seafood value-chain with state-of-the-art quality control technologies.

Task 8.1 – Market Analysis and Uptake strategy focuses on the understanding of the industry, users and value chain as the basis for the development of a business model, which will be further built during task 8.2.

This deliverable initially presents the iFMS as the combination of technologies from the two industrial consortium partners: Videometer and Scio. The two firms contribute to the project by providing and developing respectively spectral imaging instruments with their related software – the VideometerLab, VideometerLite and the VideometerLab Software with Cloud Workspaces – and a data-management platform for the tracking of seafood throughout the value-chain – Qvantum Platform.

In this introductory section, the deliverable also presents the objectives of Workpackage 8, and the methodology and data collection processes conducted for the execution of the task. Data was collected by interviewing members of the value-chain, observing them in their “real-life” context and analysing documentation provided by governmental institutions.

Task 8.1’s results are hereby presented and described in detail. The deliverable, in fact, illustrates the results of an in-depth industry analysis, carried out with models such as the Porter model and the PESTLE model. We present an accurate account of the internal and external factors that influence the industry’s profitability and competition. We, then, analyse the value chain and the hazards that afflict the seafood industry, which benefit from the use of spectral imaging, automation, and data-management.

The second section of the deliverable focuses on the role of the users and the scenarios in which they will utilize the iFMS. In the third section we present the profiles of the four main user personas, their needs, and specifications. We further investigate their daily work contexts so to analyse how the system will be utilized in real-life contexts.

In section 4 we initialize a strategic analysis of the industry. With the SWOT analysis and Key Success Factor model we bring into light the initial course of action for effective commercialization of the iFMS, and finally in section five the conclusions are made.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTELLIGENT FISH MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Aiming at advancing the seafood supply system, the TraceMyFish project bridges players from both research and industrial fields to combine their experiences for the development of a comprehensive intelligent Fish Management System (iFMS).

In order to fully exploit the commercial potential of the iFMS, the project includes (1) the detailed analysis of the seafood industry in three geographical markets: Iceland, Greece and Norway and (2) the development of a business plan and uptake strategy. Workpackage 8 focuses on the realization of these two objectives, with Task 8.1 pursuing the industry analysis, and Task 8.2 the business plan and strategy development.

This deliverable describes the specific Task 8.1 objectives, methodology and results of said analysis.

The analysis was carried out from Month 1 of the project (November 2021) to Month 9 (July 2022). The initial months were utilized to design the structure of the analysis and the data collection methodologies, while the subsequent months were employed to actively collect the data, and draw the conclusions needed for the upcoming development of Task 8.2.

The market research includes frameworks for the analysis of the industry's macroenvironment (external), the users' needs and pain points, the microenvironment (internal) and the evaluation of all factors into opportunities and success determinants.

The TraceMyFish consortium includes two industrial partners, SCiO and Videometer, each bringing their technical infrastructure and expertise towards building the envisioned intelligent Fish Management System (iFMS) that will be the final outcome of the project.

Task 8.1 takes into account the iFMS as the combination of technologies developed by Videometer A/S and SCiO. In particular, Videometer A/S contributes with the developed:

- (1) VideometerLab: Videometer's flagship spectral imaging devices, capturing high resolution images for the analysis of different products.
- (2) VideometerLite: a handheld and wireless spectral imaging device.
- (3) VideometerLab Software including Cloud Workspaces: virtual locations, which allow for the methodical storing, managing and sharing of data.

SCiO in particular will contribute by further developing:

- (1) Qvantum: an AI-driven platform that aids agri-food organizations in generating value from their data.

Figure 1 shows how these technologies will be integrated for the iFMS to function properly.

Figure 1: Configuration of the intelligent Fish Management System

1.2 VIDEOMETER'S TECHNOLOGY

Videometer is a worldwide spectral imaging provider with expertise in analysis, inspection, and quality control of a wide variety of products.

The technology behind the Videometer flagship instrument, the VideometerLab, is based on LED band-sequential spectral imaging, where a camera placed in an integrating sphere captures images sequentially with up to 20 different high-resolution bands. Because the different bands cover NIR (near infrared), visible spectrum and UV (ultraviolet) in a range between 365 and 970 nm, the images provide broad information on the product being analyzed. Examples include information on surface chemistry, color, shape, texture and more.

The VideometerLite instrument is based on the same LED band-sequential spectral imaging technology. It is a handheld, wireless device with 7 bands that range between 365 nm and 850 nm.

The VideometerLite is thought of as a fast, cost-efficient option for in-field analysis. During the duration of the TraceMyFish project it is being tested and further developed to become a stable solution for quality inspection throughout the whole seafood value chain.

The two Videometer instruments exclusively function in conjunction to the VideometerLab Software, a desktop app for the analysis of the acquired images. The system equips users with tools that combine machine learning, AI, and multivariate statistics for the processing of their images. Within the scope of the TraceMyFish project is the development of the Videometer Cloud Workspaces, which will allow software users to save, manage and

share their data in virtual cloud storages. This will accommodate remote communication between stakeholders, that has been proven to be crucial for the tracking and tracing of data.

1.3 SCiO'S TECHNOLOGY

SCiO technologies form the backbone of the data infrastructure that supports the TraceMyFish iFMS. Specifically, SCiO brings into the project its Quantum data management and analytics platform, a highly modular and extensible framework able to incorporate different data processing and analysis components tailored to the needs of any given application. Furthermore, in the case of TraceMyFish, Quantum will integrate custom analytical modules trained over on the one hand, historical measurements and, on the other hand, laboratory and field data produced in the context of the TraceMyFish pilots and targeting the fish product quality parameters defined by the piloting plan.

1.4 OBJECTIVES

TraceMyFish aspires to design and develop an iFishManagement System (iFMS) that allows interactive data browsing and incorporates visualization capabilities for monitoring and data analysis. TraceMyFish implements rapid non-destructive measures obtained by sensor technology, imaging, and spectrophotometrically data as input. By connecting such data to a blockchain-based cloud infrastructure, improved traceability and hazard monitoring will be obtained throughout the value chain.

All implemented data collection and analysis methodologies will be evaluated and calibrated by traditional chemical, physicochemical and microbiological methods to improve the accuracy of non-destructive measurements. Moreover, to make the iFMS more robust and species independent, three highly significant value chains will be studied (Atlantic salmon, Atlantic cod, and Gilthead seabream/European seabass).

In the context of the overall project scope, the objective of the market analysis presented in this report is to concretely identify the different exploitable assets produced or evolved through TraceMyFish, specify the market and user segments addressed by these assets, and formulate the best candidate approaches for reaching to these audiences for each exploitable asset.

This will be achieved via a comprehensive market research and analysis for the TraceMyFish iFMS and its individual components; the usage of key business methodologies that will determine the competitive results and their competitive advantage in the marketplace; the specification of current and future opportunities; and the identification of strategy and business model options for generating an appropriate business plan for the roll out of the iFMS and its building constituents.

1.5 PROCESS AND METHODOLOGY

Data for this deliverable was collected and analyzed in-between Month 1 (November 2021) and Month 9 (July 2022) of the TraceMyFish Project.

Data was collected with three different methodologies, which allowed for triangulation of said data:

1. Semi-structured interviews
2. Observation
3. Document analysis

1.5.1 First batch of interviews

The first set of semi-structured interviews was conducted with members of the TraceMyFish consortium. In particular, said interviews focused on the perceptions of the partners operating within an academic or research-related context. The following table (Table 1) shows the participants to the interviews.

Table 1: First batch of interview participants – research institutions

Participant name	Position	Institution
María Guðjónsdóttir	Dean and Professor at the faculty of Food Science and Nutrition	University of Iceland
Jørgen Lerfall	Professor in the faculty of Biology and Food Science	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Panagiotis Tsakanikas	Research Associate	Agricultural University of Athens

The interviews were aimed at assessing the needs and pain points of members of the value chain, specifically those who have an overview of research and development contexts. The structure for the interviews followed the template below:

Introduction:

Aim: creating trust between interviewer and interviewee.

Who am I: Alessia – Digital Marketing Specialist – Videometer A/S

Scope: Understanding their needs in regard to TMF project and VideometerLite

Confidentiality

Introduction questions:

Aim: understanding the context and building the user persona’s context.

Name:

What precisely is your role at WORKPLACE?

What do you do on a daily basis?

What skills are required for this job?

Do you work with others?

What instruments do you use?

Which one do you like the most and why?

Which one do you like the least and why?

Current methodologies:

Aim: understanding user persona's needs and feelings.

How do you assess fish traceability/quality, at the moment?

What are the most important features?

Can you describe the process?

Do you have any standards and regulations?

What are the most important ones?

How do you get samples? How do you prepare them before analysis, if you do so?

Do you have any limitations?

Why do you think you have these limitations?

Do you have any evidence or examples of limitations?

Could you rank them from most problematic to least problematic?

What works well with the current process?

Could you provide examples?

Could you rank these from most useful to least?

Are you going to share data with stakeholders? Why do you need to share data?

What are the data sharing processes at the moment? Can you describe them? (N.B. Make sure they touch upon automation and manual labor)

At the moment, are there problems with data sharing? Why? Can you give an example?

How do you think these problems could be solved?

How often do you share data with your stakeholders, at the moment? How often do you expect to share data?

What kind of data do you share with your stakeholders?

Do you organize your data, at the moment? How? Are there problems with this structure? Why? Can you give examples?

Can you explain your security protocols?

Do you use Wi-Fi or ethernet connection?

Expectations:

Aim: understanding user persona's feelings and use cases for scenarios, storyboards, and UMLs.

What is your expected use of the VideometerLite?

You have a VideometerLab and you've heard about the VideometerLite – what differences do you expect to encounter?

Do you believe you will use the instrument as portable or as stationary? Do you expect to use the VMLite without the aid of a computer (as standalone)?

How do you expect to take images of the fish?

What do you want to look at specifically in the fish? (What is more important to look at for traceability)

Is there anything interesting to visualize for fish traceability? How do you visualize that?

How do you expect to use the software?

How do you expect to share the data you gathered with VMLite with the fish value chain to enhance traceability?

How do you expect to save and then visualize the data?

I'm going to list some features. State which ones you are willing to put more effort for:

1. *Sharing of your personal data with Videometer?*
2. *Learning how to use software?*
3. *Taking courses for software and hardware use?*

I'm going to list some features from the VMLite hardware. State which ones sound more appealing for your work:

1. *Portability*
2. *Wireless*
3. *Cost*
4. *Ease of use*
5. *Spectral Imaging Technology*

What goals do you have for the use of this instrument in your daily work?

Expansion

Aim: give possibility to add more that may not have been touched upon

Do you expect other uses for the VideometerLite within other supply chains/other industries?

Are there any thoughts you would like to add that we did not touch upon?

Interviews were later manually coded based on the cumulative two-cycle method, which consists in assigning a description to portions of interviews so to convey their essence and, finally, to retrieve patterns from these codes. In order to have a holistic and detailed view of the data, this process is repeated twice (Saldana, 2010).

In the case of the interviews of this research, the first coding cycle was conducted with the Attribute Coding methodology (Saldana, 2010). The initial coding, in fact, consisted in assigning essential information to the data. More specifically, the codes referred to: demographic attributes, methodologies, products, and applications.

The second cycle, on the other hand, was conducted by using the Pattern Coding methodology (Miles et al., 2014). Pattern Coding is crucial when trying to develop major themes from a set of data and recognizing analytical units within different interviews (Miles et al., 2014).

Finally, the codes were collected into said patterns to analyse and build the user personas, their needs, and their interest in the iFMS as a tool for quality inspection and traceability.

1.5.2 Second batch of interviews and observation

The second batch of semi-structured interviews was conducted in Iceland to members of the seafood processing industry. Said interviews were conducted in collaboration with partners from the Norwegian University of Science and Technology, who were concurrently researching the value chain for Task 2.1. User Requirement Specification.

In particular, the interviews were conducted in two large Icelandic cod processing enterprises: Lysi and Brim.

- Based in Reykjavik, **Lysi** is the world’s largest fish oil producer. The company was founded in 1938 and is family owned. Lysi is part of a corporate group that owns the company Akraborg, which produces canned cod liver.

Lysi is present in 70 global markets – with expansion plans ongoing in Central and Southern America, particularly Mexico. Lysi’s domestic market accounts for 4% of their production, while export accounts for 96% of production. They operate both on a B2C-basis and on a B2B-basis, focusing mainly on bulk production for B2B.

- **BRIM** is Iceland’s leading demersal (deeper layers of the ocean) and pelagic (mid and upper layers of the ocean) fish producer.

They control a big part of their value chain, owning three vessels for catch (95% of their raw material). They process their fish and hold control over all business units for sale, marketing and supply.

BRIM focuses on the development of sustainable fishing and sets importance on this aspect of the industry.

Table 2 shows the anonymized participants to the interviews with their relative job positions and companies.

Table 2: Second batch of interview participants – members of the Icelandic seafood value chain

Participant	Job Position	Company
Participant 1	Plant Manager	Lysi
Participant 2	Quality Director	Lysi
Participant 3	Production Director	Brim
Participant 4	CEO	Brim

The interviews were structured as follows:

- Which are the most significant pain points in your company’s value chain?
- How does your company deal with them?
- What are the most common reasons for complaints?
- Please, describe your company’s routines
- Which technology and management system does your company use?

- Does your company use any on-line/at-line sensors?
- What kind of information is connected to your batch/lot?
- Which hazards are most challenging in your value chain?
- Where do you see potential for improvements?
- Are there significant bottlenecks in your current system?

The on-site visit, additionally, allowed for observation of both companies’ workflows in their natural environment. During the observation process, in-field notes were taken. Just like for the semi-structured interviews, the gathered notes were analyzed through the cumulative two-cycle coding, with the first cycle consisting of Attribute Coding and the second cycle of Pattern Coding.

1.5.3 Document Analysis

The final analysis consisted in the research and evaluation of documentation from different institutions with regulatory capacity. This analysis was especially useful for understanding the macro-environment of the seafood industry, in which the iFMS will operate. Table 3 summarizes the documents that were examined for this part of the research.

Table 3: Documents used for document analysis

Institution	Document	Year
Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)	The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture	2020
FAO	The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture	2022
FAO and World Health Organization (WHO)	Codex Alimentarius – Code of Practice for Fish and Fishery Products	Adopted 2003, Revised and Amended 2016
European Fisheries Control Agency (EFCA)	Regulation (EU) of the European Parliament and the Council of 19 March 2019 on European Fisheries Control Agency	Signed 2019, Effect 2019
EFCA	A year in review	2020
United Nations (UN)	Promotion and Strengthening of Sustainable Ocean-based Economies	2021

2 INDUSTRY ANALYSIS

2.1 SEAFOOD OVERVIEW

The seafood industry and its players hold vital importance for the development of healthy diets, and nutrition across the globe. Seafood is a key element in humans' diet, because it provides important fatty acids, such as omega-3, micronutrients, and minerals (FAO, 2022). Because of this, it is crucial to ensure that aquatic products are healthy throughout the whole supply-chain.

Throughout the decades between 1980 and 2020, the industry has undergone overall growth, except for Europe where it has seen a slight decrease with recovery in the 2020s. On average, it is estimated that human consumption reaches around 156 million tons, whereas the global fish production level is estimated to be of 179 million tons. The country producing the highest amount of seafood is China, with the Asian share of the market being of 34% (American 14%, European 10%, African 7%). The value of the seafood industry is evaluated to be over 600 billion USD.

2.2 PESTLE

Macrolevel factors have a strong influence on the well-being of a firm and its functioning, as they may have an impact on the threats and opportunities it will face. Hence, it is important to assess how these factors affect the firm's environment (Grant, 2018).

The PESTLE framework has as its main aim that of analysing macroeconomic factors that have an impact on the firm. PESTLE stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental, as these are the aspects that are taken into consideration (Grant, 2018).

2.2.1 Political

Political factors have a wide impact on the seafood industry. The FAO (2020) states in its food control system policy that it is the right of every government to ensure national food control systems, to ensure safety in the consumption and fairness of aquatic products throughout the value chain. The Codex Alimentarius (2021) regulates international food standards to ensure safety and quality, while the European Union regulates the fishing industry throughout the EU's seafood value chain with the Fisheries Control System (2019).

2.2.2 Economic

The rise in global aquaculture production rose by 527% between 1990 and 2018, and it is still growing (Fao.org, 2022). The value of the industry is expected to be 544 billion USD in 2022, with China being the largest producer (Statista.com, 2022).

As the value of the industry is constantly expanding, firms that operate within quality control of aquatic products are being positively impacted. In fact, this growth translates in hefty investments for machinery, automation, and quality assurance (Campling and Havice, 2018).

2.2.3 Social

The seafood industry and, more broadly, the food industry are impacted on social awareness of the health benefits of certain foods over others. Food trends, as well, impact the awareness that consumers have over certain ingredients. Currently, aquatic products are not only perceived as “trendy”, but also consumer awareness has developed because of the health benefits they provide (FAO, 2022).

Because of this, seafood consumption is expected to rise 18% by 2030 from the 4.3 kgs of 2020 (FAO 2022).

2.2.4 Technological

Technological impact is slowly starting to be visible in the seafood industry, which has, traditionally, been quite averse to changes. In fact, stakeholders have become more interested in advancements and innovations, due to their pay-off in efficiency and optimization of workflows and processes. Examples of these include e-monitoring, analytical prediction software, robotics and automation.

Technological advancements are also aimed at improving the sustainability objectives of fisheries by enhancing planning capacities and reducing waste (Norwegian Sea Council, 2021).

2.2.5 Legal

Safety standards are of the utmost importance in the seafood industry. e.g., FAO established the HACCP system. European Union has one of the strictest regulations regarding the number of residues (feed additives, antibiotics, contaminants), labelling, and overall quality (EU fisheries control system).

2.2.6 Environmental

The seafood industry is strongly influenced by environmental factors. Because of the growth in demand, water pollution and overfishing are rising as important issues that need to be tackled. Experts believe that the number of fisheries must decline for the sustainment of natural marine life (FAO, 2022).

As a way of contrasting these issues, different sustainability standards and labels are being issued. Many fisheries are modifying their processes to comply to these standards and improve their workflows for more feasible fishing. The expectation was to reduce overfishing and pollution by increasing the proportion of fish stocks within biologically sustainable levels (SDG 14). In the period between 2018 to 2022 75% of countries worldwide had implemented measures for sustainable fishing and aquaculture (UN, 2022).

2.3 PORTER

2.3.1 Theoretical framework

Porter's Five Forces of Competition is one of the staples for the analysis of an industry's competitiveness. This model is based on the idea that competitiveness is influenced by five sources of "pressure" – three horizontal forces: competition by substitutes, by established rivals and by entrants, and two vertical forces: power of buyers and power of suppliers (Grant, 2018).

2.3.2 Threat of substitutes

According to Porter's model (1980), the price that one is willing to pay for a given product is affected by the presence of substitutes. In fact, in the presence of substitutes, buyers will be more price-sensitive, meaning that they will be more susceptible to changes. Therefore, price-based competition is highly dependent on whether or not substitute products are available on the market.

2.3.3 Threat of new entrants

In every industry, new entrants face a number of limiting factors when approaching the market compared to the established ones. However, when an industry is profitable compared to its initial cost of capital, it will attract the onset of new players. This, in return, will change the status of the competition (Porter, 1980).

Factors that impact threat of new entrants include:

- capital requirements
- economies of scale
- absolute cost advantages
- product differentiation
- access to channels of distribution
- governmental and legal barriers
- retaliation

(Grant, 2018)

2.3.4 Rivalry among established competitors

In certain industries, companies compete aggressively between each other, pushing prices to their lowest values. In others, firms tend to base their competition on differentiation, innovativeness, and advertising.

Factors that impact rivalry among established firms are:

- concentration
- diversity

- product differentiation
- excess capacity and exit barriers
- cost conditions

(Grant, 2018)

2.3.5 Power of buyers

A company's profitability is based on the prices it sets and costs it incurs. Prices, on the other hand, are influenced among other factors by demand, thus by the behavior of the buyers. In fact, the buyers' price sensitivity and bargaining power are predominant determinants of an industry's competitiveness.

Price sensitivity depends on:

- The relative importance of a product for a buyer compared to his/her costs.
- The differentiation of the product.
- The criticalness of product compared to the buyer's need.

The bargaining power depends on:

- Size and concentration of buyers.
- Buyers' information.
- Possibility for vertical integration.

(Grant, 2018)

2.3.6 Power of suppliers

The power of suppliers can be analyzed analogously to the one of buyers, with the only difference that the companies within the industry are seen from the purchasing perspective. (Porter, 1980).

2.3.7 Five Forces of Competition for the iFMS and its Industry

As mentioned above, in the Methodology section, data for the development of such model was collected through interviews with both members of the seafood industry and members of the Videometer and Scio teams. Additional information was collected from the academia, industry reports and studies that explore both the seafood industry, the SaaS industry and the machine vision and spectral imaging industries.

2.3.8 Threat of substitutes: medium-high

Substitutes operating within the quality control of seafood exist. Usually, these substitutes provide seafood companies with traditional analytical methodologies, which are more economic compared to the iFMS, but not as powerful. For example, traditional methodologies do not allow non-destructive quality inspection, nor do they have the technical capabilities to detect certain hazards.

What makes substitutes threatening are the costs of switching from one to the other. These costs might be perceived as high, as these systems often present high cushioning costs and represent hefty investments for a firm. For this reason, we consider the threat of substitutes to be medium-high within the iFMS industry.

2.3.9 Threat of new entrants: low

It is possible to affirm that the threat of new entrants is quite low for the industry where the iFMS is operating. In fact, especially when taking into account machine vision and spectral imaging technologies, the capital costs are particularly high. Furthermore, the combination of software and hardware requires an enhanced set of skills, which is difficult to acquire in the short-term.

2.3.10 Rivalry among established competitors: low

The iFMS is one-of-its kind, because of the diverse resources it incorporates. There is no one direct competitor for the system, making the competition among existing rivals low. Furthermore, the competition is based on diversification and quality of the technology, which, in the case of the spectral imaging instrument, has been demonstrated to be superior to competitors.

2.3.11 Power of buyers: low

For sophisticated instruments such as the ones of the iFMS, buyers are not price sensitive. They do not possess the means of power to change pricing but are keener to accept higher prices for higher quality. In addition, the iFMS is not a consumer good with high concentration of buyers, but rather a system with lower demand and, hence, higher purchase costs.

2.3.12 Power of suppliers: high

Suppliers have high bargaining power in the industry, especially when it comes to hardware components. Cameras and PBCs require timely decision-making processes to purchase, particularly in the Covid-19 and Russia-Ukraine War era.

2.4 VALUE CHAIN

As previously mentioned in this deliverable, both document analysis, interviews, and observations were conducted to analyze the seafood value-chain.

Analyzing the value-chain and identifying the key nodes of these networks is crucial for the identification of potential pain points or hazards, which could be solved by the iFMS and, thus, be drivers for its commercial exploitation.

What emerged from these studies was that it is possible to build a model of the value-chain as shown in the following figure, depending on whether the fish is farmed, or sourced from the wild (Figure 2):

Figure 2: Seafood value chain

Farming: when seafood originates from aquaculture, farmers acquire seed, spat, post-larvae or juveniles to cultivate within their plants. When seed or spat is the starting point the farming process includes the in-vitro fertilization of gametes. The seafood is fed and kept at optimum conditions for its development into “adulthood”. Often, fully grown aquatic products are sold to said farms to be held at optimum conditions for commercialization.

Wild source: seafood is found in habits that allow it to reproduce and develop. On-growing, in this case, depends on survival.

Harvesting: harvesting depends not only on whether the seafood is farmed or caught in the wild, but also on its type. Different techniques exist for the various typologies of seafood that are commercialized worldwide.

Processing: just like with harvesting, different processing techniques are used for different species. However, certain processes may happen at sea: handling, packing, and freezing, in fact, can be executed on the fleet. Other processes, such as drying, are usually carried out once the seafood has been transported onto land.

Side streams: side streams are also quite dependent on the seafood species. In the Icelandic cod supply chain, for example, the remaining product after processing is utilized 100% for the making of oils or animal feeds.

Retailers: seafood is typically sold to retailers, who operate in the business-to-business (B2B) and the business-to-consumer (B2C) segments, through the auctioning of batches.

End-consumers: Finally, the seafood is individually sold to the end-consumer, who consumes it as pleased.

2.5 HAZARDS IN THE SEAFOOD SUPPLY CHAIN

As can be determined by the above description, the processes that make up the seafood value-chain are quite differentiated. This translates in wide variety of hazards and pain-points that supply-chain player may incur in. Furthermore, the Codex Alimentarius – Code of Practice for Fish and Fishery Products establishes the Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point, “a science-based system aimed at preventing food safety problems rather than having to react to non-compliance of the finished products” (FAO & WHO, 2020). This translates in strict control of aquatic products in each step of the value-chain and not just during the final stages.

The analysis of the Codex Alimentarius – Code of Practice for Fish and Fishery Products and the value-chain revealed which hazards may be detected with the use of the iFMS.

Table 4 and Table 5 illustrate the different stages of the supply-chain with the relative potential hazards and defects that can occur, and which can be traced by the iFMS.

Table 4: Hazards in general seafood supply chain

Stage	Potential Hazards	Potential Defects
Feed supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical contamination • Microbiological contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decomposition • Fungi
Growing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Chemical contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abnormal color • Physical damage
Harvesting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unlikely 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical damage or change • Biochemical change
Holding and transportation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Chemical contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical damage or change • Biochemical change
Storage and transportation of live fish	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Biotoxins • Chemical contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Death of fish • Physical damage or change • Biochemical change

Table 5: Hazards in fish processing supply chain

Stage	Potential Hazards	Potential Defects
Raw, fresh, frozen fish reception (Process 1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Viable parasites • Biotoxins • Scombrototoxin • Chemicals • Physical contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decomposition • Parasites • Physical contamination
Chilled storage (Process 2 and 14)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Biotoxins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decomposition • Physical damage

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scombrototoxin 	
Frozen storage (Process 3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Toxins • Viable parasites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dehydration • Rancidity • Loss of nutritional quality
Controlled thawing (Process 4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Biotoxins • Scombrototoxin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decomposition
Washing and gutting (Process 6 and 7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Biotoxins • Scombrototoxin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of viscera • Bruising • Off-flavors • Cutting faults • Decomposition
Filleting, skinning, trimming and candling (Process 8 and 9)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Viable parasites • Microbiological contamination • Biotoxins • Scombrototoxin • Presence of bones 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parasites • Presence of bones • Objectionable matter • Decomposition
Weighing (Process 10)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unlikely 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorrect weight
Vacuum or modified atmosphere packaging (Process 11)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsequent microbiological contamination • Biotoxins • Scombrototoxin • Physical contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsequent decomposition
Labelling (Process 12 and 18)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unlikely 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorrect labelling
Metal detection (Process 13 and 19)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metal contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unlikely
Freezing process (Process 15)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Viable parasites • Scombrototoxin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Texture deterioration • Development of rancidity • Freezer burns

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decomposition
Glazing (Process 16)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsequent dehydration • Incorrect weight
Mincing fish using mechanical separation process (Process 21)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Biotoxins • Scombrototoxin • Physical contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorrect separation (Objectionable matter) • Decomposition • Presence of defect bones • Parasites
Washing of minced fish (Process 22)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Scombrototoxin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor color • Poor texture • Excess of water • Decomposition
Blending and application of additives and ingredients to minced fish (Process 23 and 24)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical contamination • Microbiological contamination • Non-approved additives and/or ingredients • Scombrototoxin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical contamination • Incorrect addition of additives • Decomposition
Wrapping and packaging (Steps 17 and 25)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Scombrototoxin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsequent dehydration • Decomposition
Reception – packaging labels and ingredients (Process 26 and 28)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Chemical and physical contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Misdescription
Storage – packaging, labels and ingredients (Process 27 and 29)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbiological contamination • Chemical and physical contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loss of quality characteristics of packaging materials or ingredients

3 USER ANALYSIS

3.1 USER PERSONAS

Based on the results of the interviews, observation, and document analysis, it was possible to understand who the iFMS users will be and how they will interact with the system. Based on how the supply chain is structured and what has been mentioned by the respondents of the interviews, the user personas can be segmented in four groups:

- Researchers and R&D Professionals
- Seafood Processing Professionals
- Harvesters
- Retailers

In this section, we will describe each of the segments.

Researchers and R&D Professionals: This first segment includes highly educated professionals who work in laboratory settings. These individuals are used to using advanced laboratory equipment for their daily processes. They are responsible for research design and have the need to collect data in different contexts and with different instruments for the validation of their studies. At the moment, these individuals perceive only being capable of collecting data in-lab as a limitation to their work. Furthermore, they believe laboratory contexts often lack automation, which could help relieve them from hefty manual work, thus increasing efficiency. An additional pain point the researchers incur is the fact that data sharing with stakeholder can be complicated to achieve. In fact, often it is nearly impossible to share data and results with external entities to their organizations.

Seafood Processing Professionals: Processing professionals are individuals who perform highly manual tasks in factory settings. Their work includes manually assessing the seafood's quality either on-line or in-line. These activities are quite timely and subjective, allowing for misinterpretations due to human errors. Moreover, some hazards are difficult to detect with the naked eye only, like, for example, parasites or bones. The time-consuming processes translate in slower decision-making activities that are based on the seafood's quality, which can be an inconvenience in enterprises that perform multiple operations. Finally, these individuals need to ensure full transparency of their seafood's data (provenience, batch number, etc.) to fully guarantee high quality and maximize their prices, sales, and profits.

Harvesters: Harvesters often operate for the same companies of the processing professionals. This segment, though, is made up of professionals mainly working on fishing fleets. Just like the processing professionals, the harvesters need to quickly assess the quality of their seafood for decision-making activities. Harvesters, as well, need to ensure the transparency and the safety of their data, in order to guarantee the high standards of their product and be able to maximize their profits.

Retailers: Retailers operate in-market. They're objective is that of avoiding seafood fraud with unlabeled or wrongly labeled species. Moreover, they also have the need of assessing the quality and transparency of their seafood in order to guarantee high standards.

3.2 USE CASES

The above user personas analysis has brought to light different scenarios for the use of the iFMS. The research was supported both by the interviews and observations. The initial approach was that of developing different scenarios for the use of the Videometer instruments and Workspaces and the Quantum platform. These were later translated into storyboards and then into UML diagrams.

The main use cases have been identified and presented as the collection of the following storyboards.

The cloud workspace was integrated to enable users to share files in a secure and easy way. The collaboration across the whole seafood value chain is crucial to increase traceability and quality monitoring. To develop the right solution based on user needs and behaviours, UML diagrams were used. Visually mapped processes aid with understating what are the consecutive steps to ensure appropriate integration of the new feature to the Videometer Software.

The following UML diagram illustrates how stakeholders across the value chain can securely load and use the same data from a cloud Videometer workspace.

Download and load protected workspace

Figure 7: UML for Videometer Cloud Workspaces

4 STRATEGIC ANALYSIS

4.1 SWOT

The SWOT framework is one of the most widely used framework for strategy and business analysis. This model is aimed at helping firms determine their strategy for successful market entry. It is a multi-dimensional analysis that investigates the internal and external elements of a firm. In particular, it focuses on the strengths and weaknesses of a firm, as its internal factors and on the opportunities and threats, as its external factors (Grant, 2018).

In this following section, the SWOT framework for the iFMS will be illustrated.

4.1.1 Strengths

- The iFMS integrates know-how in different areas: hardware, software, cloud, data analysis.
- The iFMS is a unique system, difficult to reproduce by competitors.
- It's a complete solution fully capable of automating traceability within value chains.
- The iFMS is the result of collaboration and input from experts within research institutions and industrial settings. This enhances its functionality.
- Both industrial entities and research institutions are strong in creating loyalty and trust with our customers and stakeholders.
- The TraceMyFish consortium is small, which has resulted in good organization skills and excellent communication between partners.
- There are no direct competitors to the system as a whole.
- The connection to the EU is fundamental for the recognition and validity of the project.
- The system is both easy-to-use and cost-effective.
- The VideometerLite has a good variety of wavelengths with a good range, which allows for the gathering of essential information for quality control.
- The iFMS is user-centric, allowing for broad customization.
- The VideometerLite offers non-destructive methodologies for data analysis.
- The VideometerLite allows for faster decision making on site.
- The Videometer cloud workspaces allow for data-sharing between stakeholders and for safer, more secure data management.

4.1.2 Weaknesses

- The VideometerLite has lower image resolution compared to its sister-product, the VideometerLab.

- The iFMS is dependent on partners in different locations worldwide. Although communication is excellent between the consortium, this can result in slowing down of processes.
- The field of view of the VideometerLite instrument might be small for bigger samples.
- The iFMS is extremely dependent on suppliers in a time of uncertainty such as 2022.

4.1.3 Opportunities

- The interest in technology is rising within the seafood industry because of the current lack of it.
- There is a growing need for automation in quality control and traceability to enhanced hazard control.
- Quality control, currently, is slow and somewhat imprecise. The iFMS can help enhance precision, save time, and document processes.
- Hazard control is required by law, is extremely relevant. This allows the iFMS to position itself in the conversation.
- The VideometerLite's portability and wirelessness opens to blue-ocean strategies.
- Seafood is a “trendy food”, and the seafood industry is growing. This translates into hefty investments related to the industry.
- Cloud databases are safer than normal databases and allow for internal and external communications for customers. They also allow for more systematic work within the company.
- E-commerce might represent a new channel for the sale of the iFMS.

4.1.4 Threats

- The seafood industry is very “traditional”. It might be reluctant to changes and new technologies.
- There are many substitutes in the e-monitoring field.
- Industrial members of the seafood supply chain have not shown interest in sharing their data with other members of the value chain, while research entities have.
- The seafood industry is extremely regulated which could be a threat in the case of lobbying.
- Companies might be interested in developing their own monitoring technology.
- The Coronavirus crisis and the Russia-Ukraine war have brought difficulties for manufacturing, especially regarding the supply of parts for technological development.

4.2 KEY SUCCESS FACTORS

All the frameworks utilized in this analysis have been aimed at determining the macro and micro-environment of the iFMS. The Key Success Factors Model offers a further analysis for the systems determinants of success within the industry, combining both internal elements and external elements into one. This model answers two fundamental questions: (1) What do customers want? and (2) How does the firm survive competition? (Grant, 2018).

Table 6 shows the Key Success Factors Model applied to the iFMS.

Table 6: Key Success Factors Analysis

Demand	Competition	Key Success Factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fast quality control. • Hazard detection that is difficult to see for the naked eye. • Faster decision-making processes to allocate the right fish to the right processes. • Good support and trusting relationship with provider. • Safe data storage and documentation. • Willingness to pay higher prices for quality. • Customization of system for their product and needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competition is based on differentiation and the quality of the technology. • New entrants are not a risky threat. • Substitutes represent a riskier threat. • Suppliers have high power, especially in the current status of the world economy. • Buyers have lower power because of the technical aspects of the product. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making sure the instruments wavelengths are suitable for the application and represent a powerful tool of analysis. • Market and communicate the products technical abilities and the high quality of output. • Ability of supporting the customer post-purchase in the nurturing step of the buyer’s life cycle. • Ability to lower the customer’s time and costs for quality control and traceability. • Ability to make large scale purchases from suppliers in order to lower production costs. • Good wages for manufacturers and employees of the iFMS.

4.3 OPPORTUNITIES

Finally, the foregoing research and the data gathered throughout the interviews, observations and document analysis has brought into light a series of application opportunities which could be suitable for the uptake strategy of the iFMS. In particular, these opportunities would be suitable as basis for the development of different business cases and strategies.

The application opportunities were selected based on the capabilities of the Videometer instruments, Cloud Workspaces, and the Quantum platform. They are supported by documentation on spectral imaging applications within food safety and can be summarized as follows:

- Detection of microbiological contamination
- Viable parasites

- Physical contamination
- Fungal spoilage
- Decomposition
- Physical damage
- Presence of viscera
- Cutting faults
- Presence of bones
- Objectionable matter
- Texture deterioration
- Development of rancidity
- Freezer burns
- Poor colors
- Poor texture
- Excess of water
- Dehydration
- Toxins

The TraceMyFish project, will focus on building a research and experiment for the understanding of the viability of said applications. Working closely with members of research institutions will further validate the potential of the iFMS for quality control and traceability of seafood.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The documented work on Market Analysis, Positioning and Uptake Strategy has served as an initial analysis of the industry in which the iFMS will be operating. This task has given a holistic overview of the main components of the external and internal environment, offering a perspective over the competitiveness of the industry, the user personas and cases and the factors that could potentially lead to success, if further exploited.

Results of interviews, observations and document analysis have shown that:

1. The seafood industry is an industry in continuous growth, where increasingly more investments are made in regard to technological advancements.
2. The competitive environment for the iFMS is one with low rivalry, however, in the current economical and social environment, influenced by the Russia-Ukraine war and Covid-19 pandemic, suppliers have gained traction and bargaining power.
3. Because of the portability and flexibility of the iFMS, this tool is adaptable to users in different contexts: from field to laboratory, to retailers.
4. The iFMS users throughout the supply chain face the need of a technology that can help with hazard detection and management for safety, quality and economic reasons.
5. The establishment of the iFMS on the market should be focused on the delivery of advanced quality and safety control, and differentiation from competitors. Price competition is not pertinent to an industry with such complex operations.
6. The varied know-how provided by the TraceMyFish consortium is as strength that should be leveraged for the development of the iFMS.

The upcoming task, 8.2 Business plan, will develop the strategy for fully exploiting the iFMS' commercial potential. It will pose its basis on this analysis and facilitate the development of a Business Model Canvas and launching plan.

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